

TEACHING INFORMATION LITERACY IN CONTEXT: CASE OF CHEMICAL ENGINEERING EDUCATION

Sin-Moh Cheah & Katerina Yang

School of Chemical & Life Sciences, Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore

smcheah@sp.edu.sg

Abstract

Information literacy is an important skill for today's engineers. This paper shares the work done by the Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) Course Management Team (CMT) to introduce information literacy skills to its students, using the CDIO approach. The paper first provide some background discussion on the importance of information literacy, arguing that although it may appear to be a generic competency, it ought to be taught in the context of each engineering discipline. We outline the general approach based on the proven CDIO methodology to systematically integrated information literacy skills into a core module in the 3-year DCHE curriculum. This involves firstly the clarification of what information literacy constitutes in the CDIO syllabus, followed by the development of a full set of underpinning knowledge that clarifies what exactly the different sub-components of information literacy mean. This is followed by a faculty survey to ascertain the level of competency desired for students at the diploma-level. We then share the design of learning task where information literacy competency is embedded, ensuring that there is alignment between intended learning outcomes and the attendant assessment. In a nutshell, the learning task requires student to assess the suitability of several competing chemical processes from the sustainability standpoint. Besides assessing for factual and technical accuracy, students are required to submit a 2-page reflective journal, where among other things, they are to discuss how they have learnt to manage information effectively. The students were then surveyed on their learning experience and the results indicated that while the majority of students found the framework useful, and indicated that they will use it for other modules, there remains challenges in writing reflective journal and in using the information obtained effectively to complete the given assignment. Several ideas for moving forward with this initiative are also discussed.

Keywords: *information literacy, chemical engineering, sustainable development, CDIO*

Introduction

The key characteristic of the post industrial 21st century is that it is information abundant and intensive (Bundy, 2004). EMC, a global leader in enabling businesses and service providers to transform their operations and deliver information technology as a service, reported that the world's information is doubling every two years; and estimated that a staggering 1.8 zettabytes of information were created in 2011. It further estimated that by 2020 the world will generate 50 times the amount of information (www.emc.com, accessed Sep 2, 2013).

Mitchell Kapor, the founder of Lotus Development Corporation, famously said that "*Getting information off the Internet is like taking a drink from a fire hydrant.*" This statement clearly reflects the challenge one faced when searching for information in the world wide web. Today's individuals are faced with diverse information choices in their studies, in the workplace, and in their lives. Information is available through community resources, special interest organizations, manufacturers and service providers, media, libraries, and the internet. Increasingly, information comes unfiltered. This raises questions about authenticity, validity, and reliability. In addition, information is available through multiple media, including graphical, aural, and textual. These pose special challenges in evaluating, understanding and using information in an ethical and legal manner. The uncertain quality and expanding quantity of information also pose large challenges for society. Pope (2009) reported on the perhaps not so surprising discovery that despite the vast resources now easily available to students on the World Wide Web, many students have difficulty with using this resource. She reported that students "tend to either not know where to start or choose literature that is too narrow (non-survey technical articles), which they have difficulty understanding. Other groups favor survey articles and wikipedia entries without seeking more in-depth knowledge, which leads to a surface understanding that prevents them from addressing challenges they face during their project."

Sheer abundance of information and technology will not in itself create more informed citizens *without* a complementary understanding and capacity to use information effectively (Bundy, 2004). Information literacy is thus required because of the ongoing

proliferation of information resources and the variable methods of access. According to the American Library Association, information literacy is the ability to "recognize when information is needed and have the ability to locate, evaluate, and use effectively the needed information" (ACRL, 2000). Here, we would like to take a broader view espoused by the UNESCO (Abid, 2004):

"Information literacy forms the basis for lifelong learning. It is common to all disciplines, to all learning environments and to all levels of education, while recognizing the disparities in learning styles and in the nature and development of literacy in different countries. It enables learners to master content and extend their investigations, become more self-directed, and assume greater control over their own learning, information literacy should be introduced wherever possible within national curricula as well as in tertiary, non-formal and lifelong education."

Figure 1. Relationship of information literacy to lifelong learning

Information Literacy and Engineering Education

Rosenzweig and Gardner (1994) reported on their survey in *Chemical Engineering Progress* that, "chemical engineers today spend a considerable amount of time retrieving and using information on a wide variety of topics..." but, "depended on personal collections and other engineers for their information, and were not making good use of the growing number of electronic options. More than half the survey respondents attributed this to their inability to find and use appropriate information".

The electronic options no doubt had grown tremendously since Rosenzweig and Gardner cited their findings. However, the ability of our students to effectively make use of freely available information afforded by the Internet had apparently not kept up with such development. For example, a recent report by Mullen and Kajiwara (2002) noted that: "...experiences in the engineering classrooms have taught us that the students have not kept up with the changes. The students have discovered the Internet but do not use it in a sophisticated way". This need is especially more important today, in particular for engineering curriculum that adopted the CDIO approach where a basic-level design-implement experience is introduced in the very first year of curriculum (CDIO, 2010) as a way to make learning engineering more interesting. The importance placed on information literacy can be exemplified by a

survey of professional engineers conducted by Mosberg et al (2005) who noted that, of the 23 items deemed important in engineering design, "seeking information" was the fourth highest rated, behind "understanding problem", "constraints" and "communicating".

Candy (2002) noted that although information literacy appears to be a generic competency, it is however, also a strong context-dependent element as well. He noted that "while there may be some aspects of information literacy that can be applied irrespective of the particular field of study, it is also the case that a person who is more expert than another in any given field or study or practice is likely to have a more well-developed sense both of where relevant information is to be located, and how it may be retrieved and evaluated." Various authors had henceforth called for the need to include information literacy in teaching of engineering programs (Lickie & Fullerton, 1999; Pilerot & Hiort af Ornäs, 2006; Breen et al, 2010).

The CDIO Way: Integrating Information Literacy into Chemical Engineering Curriculum

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) in Singapore Polytechnic (SP) had adopted CDIO as the basis of its chemical engineering education since 2006. Recognizing the importance of information literacy in the education of our students, we embark on an initiative to integrate information literacy into our curriculum. Prior to this, information literacy is only taught to students as part of their Year 3 Final Year Project workshop, to better prepare them in carrying out literature review.

We are now embarking on a new initiative to integrate information literacy into core modules. We selected the Year 3 module *Chemical Reaction Engineering*, the topic of which is familiar to both of us. For this initiative, we used the same tried-and-tested approach that we used in part efforts to integrate various CDIO skills into our chemical engineering curriculum (Cheah, Phua & Ng, 2013). We firstly consulted the relevant section of the CDIO Syllabus, which in this case, is Section 2.2 "Experimentation, Investigation and Knowledge Discovery" under Part 2 "Personal and Professional Skills and Attributes":

- 2.2.2 Survey of Print and Electronic Literature
The literature and media research strategy
Information search and identification using library, on-line and database tools
Sorting and classifying the primary information
The quality and reliability of information

As in other earlier approaches, we handled the effort firstly by asking the two key questions posed by Crawley et al (2007) before proceeding to design the learning task that inculcates the necessary skill set:

- What is the full set of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that engineering students should possess as they leave the university, and at what level of proficiency?
- How can we do better at ensuring that students learn these skills?

For the first question, we turn to UNESCO for the information literacy needs in Figure 2, which show 8 sub-component or skill sets.

Figure 2. Information Literacies (UNESCO)

Crawley et al (2007) identified five levels of proficiency for a given CDIO skill:

1. To have experienced or been exposed to
2. To be able to participate in and contribute to
3. To be able to understand and explain
4. To be skilled in the practice or implementation of
5. To be able to lead or innovate in

For information literacy, our survey among the 24 faculty placed it at an average value of 3.6, which we felt is acceptable for diploma-level graduate. We then developed the underpinning knowledge for each of the sub-component skill set. We felt that, although on the surface such skill sets appear self-explanatory, there is a need to explicitly elaborate on what each means, supplemented by relevant examples in the context of chemical engineering. An example of the underpinning knowledge for “Locate and evaluate information“ is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Sample Underpinning Knowledge

After you found what seemed like the stuff you are looking for, you now need to evaluate if you have gotten the *relevant* information. In the case of chemical processes for instance, the relevant information would be processes that shows potential at least at the pilot scale, if not already available commercially. It should not include processes that had only been studied in the lab, or merely those of intellectual curiosity or theoretical possibility. Also, if you are comparing different processes from sustainability point of view, be mindful that you must look at each process holistically, i.e. considering all the factors listed in the earlier paragraph. For example, an endothermic processes operating at high temperature and pressure is less sustainable compare to one that requires lower temperature and pressure. As another example, a process that produces harmful waste or side product that is difficult to separate tend to be less sustainable as well.

Next, we designed a student-centered learning task that simulate a real-world scenario (see Table 2) where students need to evaluate a given process for the production of the ethyl acetate (Figure 3), against other competing processes, from the sustainability point of view. This task requires them to use the Internet or Library to search for the necessary information in order to complete the task at hand.

Table 2. Selected Section of Case Scenario

As part of the company expansion strategy, *PureX Chemicals* is interested in entering the attractive market of supplying ethyl acetate. Ethyl acetate is widely used in the chemical processing industry as solvent. The plan is to utilize a new technology of ethanol dehydration-dehydrogenation to produce ethyl acetate. Mr. Chin Bo Yeong told you:

“Find out more about this new technology and include any suitable flowsheet to illustrate the process. Do check up on other existing method(s) of ethyl acetate production, and make an evaluation if the new technology is more desirable from a sustainability perspective.”

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“Based on your findings, prepare a set of PowerPoint slides for my presentation to Senior Management.”

Figure 3. Learning Task for Activity on “Role of Chemical Reaction Engineering in Sustainable Development”

The learning task was designed in a manner to ensure alignment between learning outcomes, learning strategy and assessment, as shown in Figure 4. Some of the relevant learning outcomes are shown in Table 3, notably the ability to demonstrate competency in information literacy, in the context of sustainable development. They are also expected to use critical thinking skills in evaluating the information obtained.

Students then work together cooperatively to complete the task. As can be seen in Table 2, we also integrated other CDIO skills such as designing a communication strategy to convey their findings, in this case, a PowerPoint presentation to the company's senior management.

Figure 4. Curriculum alignment model for integrated learning task

Table 3. Selected Learning Outcomes

(a).	Demonstrate information literacy in searching, evaluating and organizing data
(b).	Compare and contrast different chemical processes to produce a given product (in this case, ethyl acetate)
(c).	Assess the sustainability of chosen process
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(f).	Apply the good communication principles in the design of PowerPoint slides

Goodwin (2003) argues that assessment driven students are more likely to develop their information literacy skills. In this case, we assessed the students for the quality of their submission and discern from their answers (in their evaluation of sustainability of different processes) if they are able to process and evaluate the information gathered. They are also required to submit individual reflective journal to help them review their information literacy. This is shown in Table 4.

Evaluation of Student Learning Experience

We conducted a simple survey to ascertain students' perceived usefulness of the information literacy framework. We use a 5-point Likert scale ranging from '5' for 'Strongly Agree' to '1' for 'Strongly Disagree'; for the following questions:

1. The Information Literacy Framework is easy to understand and use
2. The guidelines given in the Information Literacy Framework is useful to me in getting to the information that I needed
3. I can use the Information Literacy Framework to help me in other assignments in my course of study
4. Overall, the Information Literacy framework is useful in helping me complete my assignment.

Table 4. Selected Assessment for Learning Task

PowerPoint Presentation – Technical Content

Evaluation of the ethanol dehydration-dehydrogenation method with other different method(s) of ethyl acetate production, from sustainability point of view. Include any relevant chemical reaction equations and flow diagram, if available. (8 marks)

NOTE: Refer to the *CDIO Learning Guide* for more information on "Digital Literacies" to help you filter out and decide on what information to include in your answer.

Reflective Journal:

Managing Learning (incl. Digital Literacies)

(Reminder: This is an *individual* submission, by uploading to the module Blackboard site) (16 marks)

For this part of the assessment, you are to reflect on how you have managed your own learning to complete this activity, whereby the topic is probably new and not explicitly taught to you. In *no more than two A4 pages* (Arial, 12-point font), appraise how well you have managed your learning in terms of the following:

- The role of played by chemical reaction engineering in sustainable development
- Set goals, worked with team members and managed time
- Strategies and resources used to support learning
- Monitored learning (including information literacy) and made changes where necessary
- Improvements to managing learning that you could make in future

You are encouraged to support your claims made in the journal with specific relevant examples from the activity.

As the students worked on the learning task in turns, with one group of 4-5 students every alternative week, we administer the survey immediately at the conclusion of their lab session. At the time of this paper submission, the lessons are still continuing; and 4 groups of students had completed the learning task, with a total of 16 students surveyed.

Results and Discussion

Results from our survey shows that majority of the students (80.0% Agree or Strongly Agree) found the information literacy framework useful as indicated in Figure 5. However, not all the students who reported that the framework is useful agreed that the guidelines given are useful, as shown in Figure 6. Here the percentage of students who felt neutral about this statement is significant at 35.7%. Despite this, many (78.5% Agree or Strongly Agree) felt that they can use the framework for other assignments in their study, as shown in Figure 7. Overall, 71.4% of the students are satisfied with the information literacy framework. This percentage is not as high as we expected, indicating that there are areas of improvement that we need to undertake to improve the framework and/or the learning experience.

Figure 5. Usefulness of Information Literacy Framework

Figure 6. Usefulness of Underpinning Knowledge

Figure 7. Confidence in using Framework

Figure 8. Overall Usefulness of Framework

As these are preliminary results only, we will do another update when all students had completed the activity. Among other things, we hope to be able to identify the students who feedback negatively about the framework and/or learning experience with the view of addressing any shortcomings in the framework and/or learning task. This can be done through a focus group discussion, whereby we seek for volunteers especially those who replied “Neutral” or “Disagree” in their responses. The challenge is to convince these students that their final module grades will not be compromised, or else we carry out the focus group discussion after the examinations.

Also, from the reflective journals submitted we can see that the students are able to appreciate the usefulness of the framework. For example, one student noted that: “The framework provides general steps to take when you are trying to look up for certain information. In summary, I need to firstly search and sort the obtained information. Secondly, I need to evaluate the information whether they are relevant to what I needed. Lastly, organize the information I have gotten and save the source for easy retrieval.” However, we also noted that the students can do better in terms of writing the learning points in the journals.

Next, from the 4 sets of PowerPoint slides received from the students thus far, we have somewhat mixed results. Some groups had clearly have demonstrated that they were able to evaluate the methods of production from sustainability point of view by comparing the feedstock used, the submissions from others obviously have some room for improvements.

Lastly, we identified several areas of improvement that can be carried out to further improve the framework and learning task:

- (1) Use of rubrics for assessment: we need to introduce suitable rubrics to ensure consistency in the marking process as administered by different lecturers taking the different classes. The rubrics also communicate to students our expectations.
- (2) To introduce in other Year 3 modules learning tasks that require the use of information literacy without explicitly linking this to the framework, to evaluate if the students can effectively use it and demonstrate the same level of competence, if not higher.
- (3) To expand the range of examples in the underpinning knowledge: we plan to add more examples to the key underpinning knowledge in the information literacy so that students can easily use it for other core modules such as rotating equipment, heat transfer and equipment, etc.
- (4) To share the model with other lecturers and to work with them to introduce the model to students especially at the earlier years of study, preferably from Year 1.
- (5) Depending on our evaluation of the remaining submissions from the rest of the students, we need to explore ways to improve their competency in making in-depth analysis of the information obtained.

Conclusions

This paper presented our initial effort at integrating information literacy into a core module of our chemical engineering curriculum. Initial results from students' responses to the survey indicated that students possess sufficient Information Literacy skills to carry out learning tasks required. For example, one student noted in the reflective journal that "not all the resources can be trusted. We need to have enough proves and compare different resources to check on the validity of a particular information. In this activity, we did examine our results by looking on different resources. We need to have enough knowledge so that any wrong statement on the website can be eliminated in our work."

In addition to searching information from the internet, students also use other online platforms and tools, such as Google Drive and Skype to share information with each other to complete the learning tasks. This does not eliminate the fact that the students still meet face-to-face at least once before the final submission is made.

However, it remains questionable whether the students are able to contextualise the information that they search from the internet to the questions that they need to complete in an assignment. This is evident when the students submit their work where some of the answers indicate surface understanding only. This indicates that they still lack in-depth analysis and capacity to use information effectively. This also means that the integration of information literacy into core modules of our chemical engineering curriculum must be done in a meaningful way so that students learn to seek for more in-depth knowledge and understanding.

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